

The Buying Behavior Influence of Consumers in Hosur Municipality

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Abstract

Powerful brands create meaningful images in the minds of consumers with brand images serving as a means of differentiation from the competition and thus positively influencing customer's purchasing behavior. Branding plays a vital role to boost up any business performance, is a disguised tool which can confidently change people's buying behaviors. In the current marketing scenario, the Study of Consumer Behavior has become important. Without consumers, no business organization can run. All the activities of the business concerns end with consumers and consumer fulfillment. Customer behavior study is based on consumer buying behavior, with the customer playing the three distinct roles of user, payer and buyer. Consumer buying behavior has become an essential part of strategic market planning. The objectives of the study focus on examine power of branding on consumer buying behavior, to find out if consumer buying behavior is influenced by factors such as premium price of branded goods, perceived quality of branded goods, social status and brand name associated with the consumption of brand in Hosur municipality and the study will base on mobile electronics.

Keywords: Brand, Consumer Behavior, Buying, mobile electronics

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Introduction

Background to the Problem

People in our society are so conscious about their status and they prefer to use branded products to show off their status symbol. The brand is considered as the implied device through which any business can attain the attraction of people and can enjoy the competitive edge. In our local scenario, it also considered as a valuable asset for any business as it can change peoples' buying behavior. It can play a vital role to expand any business. Marketing valuable strategies and tools can develop the brand of any product. If the brand is managed in effective ways, a business can enjoy the maximum number of customers and can build long-term profitable relations with customers. Refine quality of products and social responsibilities of any business can positively affect the behaviors of people regarding the brand image, satisfaction and loyalty.

The market is flooded with new and old brands and strength of brand war is increasing day by day. The popularity of a brand is an instrument for the survival and success of the company in the market. In this respect, companies present different packages to customers with the use of different resource weapons in this rivalry war for

raising awareness among the customers about the branded product. While studying the literature, it was found out that there is not much research about branding and consumer behavior. Most research is focused on more complicated knowledge structures such as attitude, awareness and brand image as Factors Influencing Consumer Buying Behavior of Luxury Branded Goods (Khor eng tatt 2010) from University Sains Malaysia and a study to indicate the importance of brand knowledge in brand choice- A cultural perspective (Fred Posner, 2005) from Kristianstad University. Therefore, this research focuses on the brand and how it affects consumer's pick.

Statement of the Problem

Consumers have their attributes and forces behind before and during the process of purchasing branded goods/product. If customers trust a brand quality it makes a positive connection to the brand and customers will have a reason to become loyal to the brand. Loyalty and trust of the customers are very important for a company because it reduces the chance of attack from competitors (Aaker, 1996). In this increasable competitive market, companies are attempting to gain the better position for them by becoming more customer-oriented (Hartmann, 2007). Companies are facing the wider range of competitors who offer a similar product to the same customers at different prices (Kotler, 2005). Usually, most of the products lack differentiation, competitors and potential competitors are also like to copy what the leading company does. Usually, we get information and knowledge during our life. This depends on our judgment and beliefs. As things like education, work and other factors have a continuous influence on human life. Human judgment and beliefs change over time. A good strategy differentiates company brand to other competitor's brands. The intention to offer a marketing package for consumer benefits by a marketer is to win the competition by creating new and decisive consumer value (Welibacher, 1993).

Objectives of the Study

The general objective of this study is to focus on the influence of branding on consumer buying behavior. This study intends to find out if consumer buying behavior is influenced by factors such as the premium price of branded goods, perceived quality of branded goods, societal status and brand name associated with the consumption of brand.

Within this paper, the specific objectives of the research were to reveal i) the importance of branding when it comes to consumers' buying decision ii) the importance of branding when assessing the perceived risk associated with the purchase,

The purposes of this study are to evaluate how branding and its branding strategy are impacting consumer buying behavior. In evaluating the statement, this study attempts to answer the following questions:

1. What are the factors influence consumer buying behavior on branded goods?
2. What are the importances of branding when it comes to consumers buying decision?

The Significance of the Study

This study is exploring the relations between variables that affect the buying decision of consumer on brands. Understanding of variables such as price, quality, brand name and societal status if can help further understand how these variables affect the choice making of the consumer. This study helps the present Marketing Managers to better reposition their brands and advertising strategy to capture the correct target market to improve the sales in times where the economy is at a challenge. With such a study, the impact on the advertisement is an influential media to promote branding of products and variables that influence buying decisions is surely a focus to ensure the Marketing Communications are done correctly and effectively. Ensuring effective execution of

strategy are by understanding how variables such as pricing, quality, perceived societal status and brand name could influence consumer buying behavior of branded goods.

The Scope of the Study

This research focuses on the influence of branding on consumer buying behavior in Hosur. This location is strategic because the city is blessed with different types of industries and multi-cultural differences hence it is simple to collect data as due to a large number of people living in this city. This study employs just one different item in different industries and will base on consumer only.

Limitations of the Study

The biggest challenges of this study were: - Data availability, the ability of a user to access information or resources in a specified location and the correct format. This is the main problem with using questionnaires as a method of data collection. Due to the fact that this is not a face to face interview kind of questions, sometimes the respondents might not be willing to give exact answers to some questions and they may refuse to respond to a question on the grounds that they are scared of what will be done with the questionnaire, either will send directly to the responsible companies.

Bureaucracy, this is another problem that the researcher was faced during the fieldwork. Some respondents were not able to provide data until they got permission from their superior. Even though bureaucracies sometimes seem inefficient or wasteful, setting up a bureaucracy helps ensure that thousands of people work together in compatible ways by defining everyone's roles within a hierarchy. The procedures in place to prevent disclosure of confidential data, including rules applying to staff, aggregation rules when disseminating data, provision of unit records some of the respondents were not providing their true opinions during the interviews because they regard some of the questions as sensitive. However, this group was small and the researcher assumed it did not affect the overall results and conclusions.

Literature Review

A good literature review gathers information about a particular subject from many sources. It is well written and contains few if any personal biases. It should contain a clear search and selection strategy (Carnwell and Daly, 2001). Good structuring is essential to enhance the flow and readability of the review. Accurate use of terminology is important and jargon should be kept to a minimum. Referencing should be accurate throughout (Colling, 2003). The Consumer behavior study involves how an individual or groups select, purchase, use or dispose of products, services ideas, or experience to satisfy their need and desires. The environmental features are, for instance, comments are taken from other customers, advertising, packing, price, and product appearance, etc. (Paul & Jerry C, 2005 pg 5).

The behavior can be analyzed in different ways, by offering the lower price, better service and good quality. (Papanastassiou and Rouhani, 2006). Furthermore, it also sheds light on how the consumers evaluate the products after the purchase and the effect of evaluations on their future purchases. (Schiffman Kanuk, P.08).

The consumer engages in extensive information to search and to learn about product category to be able a good purchase decision. For example, when a consumer decides to buy a car, he seeks information about the available brands and compares his collected information about each brand and finally makes up his mind. (Kotler and Armstrong, 2003 pp. 276-277) After the purchasing consumer might experience post-purchase dissonance (after sales discomfort).⁸⁶ (Kotler, and Armstrong, 2003 p.277).

If the consumers keep buying for the same brand over and over again, it becomes their habit. It is as if that the consumers have developed a brand loyalty for that specific brand rather they buy the product out of habit. Generally speaking, consumers are usually lowly involved when the product is cheap. (Kotler, Wong, Saunders, Armstrong, p.277). Uggla (2001), explain consumer behavior into two different types, i.e., cognitive and experience oriented. The consumers who have cognitive behavior are rational and logical consumers while the experience oriented consumers have more emotional motives for buying a product.

In comparison, Dalqvst and Linde (2002) have defined four types of consumer behavior: rational, unconscious, learned and social behavior. The different behaviors are characterized by order of three steps: knowledge, attitude and action. Learned behavior: reflexes settle the choice of product. When the consumers choose a product they do not plan their choice; they do it by habit. This behavior usually occurs when consumers buy the newspaper.

Research Methodology

Various research methodologies were used in the whole process of undertaking research around the area occupied consumers. The research methodologies include research design, the population of the study, sampling techniques and sample size, data collection procedures, the reliability and validity precautions are taken. Finally, it explains the ethical considerations that the researcher takes into account.

This research uses qualitative research approach and employs the descriptive statistical approach in SPSS; the aim is to quantify data regarding numbers (a numerical representation of information) obtained from respondents in the course of various ways including the use of questionnaires to attain tables and numbers, which are in percentage form. Furthermore, Qualitative research approach assists to produce findings not arrived using statistical procedures. It dealt with opinions and attitudes of respondents.

Hosur is a City in the Indian state of Tamil Nadu. It is the largest city in the Krishnagiri District of Tamil Nadu and is the headquarters of the Hosur Taluk. According to 2011 census, Hosur had a population of 116,821 with a sex-ratio of 968 females for every 1,000 males, much above the national average of 929.[5] A total of 14,307 were under the age of six, constituting 7,274 males and 7,033 females. The population of the study was 1200 consumers. A detailed description of the population of consumer buying behavior city region picked from the respective area. This location is strategic because the city is blessed with different types of industries and multi-cultural differences hence it is simple to collect data as due to a large number of people living in this city. In this research the sample size is 250, the sample depends on gender, age, location and budget.

The selected sample size for the study is 250 consumers (using purposive sampling technique) belong to the Hosur Town. The justification behind the selection of 250 as a sample size is purposive sampling technique allowed the author to take the smart set of respondents. There is the advantage of purposive sampling technique over a probability technique that is “depth info” from the respondents (Patton, 2005). Respondents that required for the study are consumer those know the branding products concept. Purposive sampling permits to select such kind of respondents (Bernard, 2011; Lewis & Sheppard, 2006). Non-probability sampling (purposive sampling) is not against of the theory of probability; if it does not negate the probability theory, hence it is not against the concept of generalizability (Teddlie & Tashakkori, 2003).

Primary data were collected from the selected respondent using interview and questionnaire methods on factors influencing consumer buying behavior on branded goods.

The secondary data were collected from official documents and reports. Data included identification of branded goods products. Both the open-ended questionnaires and closed-ended

questionnaires will be used to obtain both quantitative and qualitative data from the sources. This method covered a wide range area, and it responds in a short time, it minimizes costs and no bias on both sides.

Data Presentation, Analysis and Discussion Of Findings

Analysis of data and research findings have been interpreted about the objectives of the study and concerning the research questions developed to guide the study. In analyzing the data collected, the research used both quantitative and qualitative techniques. Quantitative data analysis involves the use of mathematical measures such as total and percentage while qualitative data analysis, on the other hand, involves logical reasoning, interpretation, comparison and explanations of the study findings. In this manner, most of the logical reasoning was based on marketing principles and the overall marketing operation in general. Most of relevant of these findings to support the research objectives are discussed here and the report ends by providing various recommendations and conclusions.

Characteristics of Responses on Gender, Age, Brand Selection and Brand Used

Questionnaires collected total (236) out of (250) distributed, equivalent to (94.4%) while (14) Questionnaires equivalent (5.6%) was not collected due to the several reasons.

The term “gender” distinguishes the set of learned expectations, behaviors, and attitudes about being a man or woman from our biologically determined traits collectively termed our sex.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Male	121	48.4	51.27	51.27
	Female	115	46	48.73	100
	Total	236	94.4	100	
Missing	System	14	5.6		
	Total	250	100		

The study found that both genders were involved in data collection and thus the findings could not suffer from gender biases. That means, both of them are engaged in branding and consumer buying behavior, both are in the same position to acquire what they wanted.

The time of life when a person becomes qualified to assume certain civil and personal rights and responsibilities, usually at 18 or 21 years, so we use different ages to make sure research conducted and responded to all people, there is no bias as the table below shown the inclusion of different ages. This will make the research clear because there are no complaints of bias in age.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	15 - 20	55	23.31	51.27	51.27
	21 - 30	28	11.86	48.73	100
	31 - 40	2268	9.32	100	
	41 -50	63	28.81		
	50+	236	26.69		
Missing	Total	14	100		
	System	250	5.6		

Also, the study employs respondents of different age to get wide answers concerning the subject. According to the table above the age of 15-20 were 55 equivalent to (23.31%), 21-30

were 28 equivalent to (11.86%), 31-40 were 22 equivalent to (9.32%), 41-50 were 68 equivalent to (28.81%) and 50+ and they are 63 equivalent to (26.69%), generally 41-50 group have many respondents compared to other groups but different age group employed in this research.

As well the study intends to understand the reason behind as to why the consumer chooses different brands, what particularly inside them force them to choose, which means people choose brands they wanted due to different reasons that made them choose. There are so many reasons but in this research, respondents were allowed to choose what was directed in the questionnaire and if the reason is not there, they are also allowed to state what it is.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Brand Name	95	38	40.25	41.2
	Quality	88	35.2	37.28	38.3
	Availability	22	8.8	9.32	12.4
	other	31	12.4	13.13	100
	Total	236	94.4	100	
Missing	System	14	5.6		
Total		250	100		

According to the questionnaire there is, brand name were 95 respondents said it is the reason influence them in a brand choice equivalent to (38.0%), 88 respondents equivalent to (35.2%) they choose quality as the reasons for the choice of brand, compared to 22 respondents equivalent to (8.8%) they choose availability of the item as the reason influence them, while the other 31 equivalents to (12.4%) said there are other reasons influence them such as taste, the first brand to enter in the market, price, income and other. According to the table above according to this research, most of the respondents said the quality is the most attribute they prefer when it comes to the choice of the brand.

Frequency is defined as the number of times that a customer has purchased from a seller. It is an integral part of the trilogy called Recency, Frequency, Monetary (RFM) analysis that is used to predict customer response in direct marketing promotions. Frequency is often a powerful predictor of response, but it is seldom as powerful as Recency. We can easily illustrate the differences by comparing the response rates of the same group of people based on their recency and their frequency (unknown).

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	1	52	22	20.8	20.8
	2-5	60	25.5	24	49.6
	5+	124	52.5	49.6	100
	Total	236	94.4	100	
Missing	System	14	5.6		
Total		250	100		

Consumer behavior prefers the brand they use several times before; this is because they avoid perceived risk on the new one. The table above shows that 52 respondents equivalent to (22%) they buy the brand the use once and they can choose a brand even if it was the first time either to use or in the market but they are confident to choose and use, these are risk taker, compared to second group where they say they use such a brand 2-5 times where 60 respondents equivalent to (25.5%) they respond and say they prefer the brand they use several times and the can use it as long as they

want because they have confidence, while the last group they prefer the brand they use more than 5, 124 respondents equivalent to (52.5%) said they like brands they use most of the time because it gives them confidence and trust, so many people in this research prefer brands they use several times. The frequency of purchasing shows the customer loyalty of such a brand.

Summary of the Study

Branding activities are guided by principles which have to be adhered to. The influence of branding on consumer buying behavior can be assessed from the preferably attribute the consumer desire. This study intends to find out the influence of branding on consumer buying behavior especially at Kinondoni Municipality and it is based on consumers only and not branding company. The required data relating to different variables of the study were gathered by distributing questionnaires to 50 consumer's respondents. The data collected were processed and analyzed by the use of percentages. On the finding, it was observed that although there are different and many attributes quality is the best attribute most of the respondents said influence them. The conclusions emerged out of the study were presented here under.

Conclusion

Conditions of competition are changing rapidly today and companies that strategize and react to these changes promptly and quickly are the most successful. Due to technological developments, physical differences between products have decreased. Differentiation should be made on the meanings products bear instead of on their physical features. A successful brand differentiation can be possible by building personality. Thanks to brand personality, the consumer sees the brand as the friend since it provides him with emotional benefits.

Overall, it is argued that the study of consumer behavior is rapidly evolving as researchers recognize and implement new techniques and trans-disciplinary perspectives to understand the nature of purchase and consumption behavior. This wider view attempts to study consumer behavior in the light of rapidly evolving lifestyles, values, priorities, and social contexts. Various theories on consumer research were not tested empirically until the middle twentieth century. The distinctly practical emphasis awaited the development of the field of marketing in the business curriculum. In particular, the buying process of consumer behavior is of more importance to marketing practitioners than the consumption process.

The conclusion emerged out of this study are presented objective wise. Based on the findings of the two research questions that is, does premium price influence the buying behavior of consumer branded goods? Does perceive the quality associated with the brand will influence the buying behavior of consumer branded goods? Does the social status of owning a branded goods influence the buying behavior of consumer on branded goods? Does brand name influence the buying behavior of consumer on branded goods? It can be concluded that:

When answering the question, It was found that, premium price influence consumer buying behavior on branded goods, it is the important factor that can identify the quality of the brand. Respondents believe that even when they purchase at the first unknown brand, the price may lead them. Also, the price is important as brand awareness for their choice of brand. Among other factors, the premium price is the important factor for brand choice both at the first purchase and the purchase today. We believe that choosing the brand that has the high price, is a sign of security and safe for decision making. However other attributes like quality can be linked to premium price in the way that the consumers have confidence in such a brand. In that case, the premium price is still the most important factor in brand choice.

Scope for Further Research

The current study was based on one industry only in one district from Hosur, Krishnagiri district. Therefore, the result cannot be generalized to other larger or much different cities of Tamil Nadu. I think further research can be done on a large scale with large sample size not only in Hosur, Krishnagiri district, but also covering other products or in other cities concerning one specific industry. I found some interesting facts, among them one is that a well-known brand name is more popular than the unknown brands. People have a high awareness of the well-known brand. Majority of customers prefer to purchase a well-known brand products. Therefore customers do not want to take any risk to purchase unknown brands. Even if the study shows that people's first preference is to purchase branded products but I cannot apply this result to other studies. Further research can be conducted in this area for finding the broad answers that this result can be used for all studies.

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